

maximum net return to labor under one irrigation. Wheat was the most economical under two and three irrigations. The net return to labor under three irriga-

tions was nearly equal for wheat and safflower.

At Baronda, only wheat and safflower produced profitable net returns to labor.

Wheat yield increased with number of irrigations. The maximum safflower yield was obtained with one irrigation. Wheat was the most profitable. ■

Environment and its influence

Flowering behavior of ratooned photoperiod-sensitive rices

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Ratooning photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties during the dry season may avoid flood or water stagnation damage in low-lying flood-prone areas during the wet season. Both the main crop and its ratoons must be photoperiod sensitive in such a cropping system. A preliminary study of flowering behavior was conducted in RRS (22°52'N) fields at Chinsurah in 1980-81.

Six photoperiod-sensitive, traditional tall indica rice varieties — NC365, FR 13A, Achra 108/1, Nagra 41/14, SR26B, and Bansmoti aman — sown the first week of November 1980 flowered in late March or early April. Each variety was ratooned at maturity in May. The ratoons of FRI3A, SR26B, and Achra 108/1 showed another flush of flowering in early June. The ratoons of NC365 and Bansmoti aman did not flower till October. The ratoon of Nagra 41/14 flowered irregularly throughout the growing period. All varieties showed further vegetative growth and flowered the third week of October (see table). Three distinct types of flowering behavior and related photoperiod are shown in the figure.

The flowering behavior of ratoons was not different from that of the normal July sowing.

Varietal differences in ratoon flower-

Flowering behavior of photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties and their ratoons grown during the 1981 dry season in West Bengal.

Variety	Main crop 50% flowering date	Ratoon flowering 1st flush	Growth phase (Jun-Sep)	Ratoon full flowering 2d flush	Normally sown crop full flowering
NC365	28 Mar	nil	Vegetative	24 Oct	25 Oct
Bansmoti aman	24 Mar	nil	Vegetative	22 Oct	22 Oct
SR26B	4 Apr	1-7 Jun	Vegetative ^a	22 Oct	25 Oct
Achra 108/1	6 Apr	1-7 Jun	Vegetative ^a	22 Oct	25 Oct
FR13A	6 Apr	6-15 Jun	Vegetative ^a	22 Oct	24 Oct
Nagra 41/14	8 Apr	Jun-Oct irregular	Flowering	—	23 Oct

^aAfter flowering, 1st flush ratoon showed further vegetative growth.

Flowering behavior of photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties and their ratoon under different photoperiods. A = NC365, B = Achra 108 1, C = Nagra 41/14 and, R = ratoon.

ing offer a criterion for selection of varieties for this cropping system. Bansmoti aman and NC365 appear to be suitable,

as they did not show any intermediate or irregular flowering after main crop harvest. ■

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